

A NOTE ON THE USE OF ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN ACIDIMETRY AND ALKALIMETRY.

By SACHINDRA NATH ROY.

In two previous papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 486 ; 1937, 14, 120), the applicability of adsorption indicators in acidimetry and alkalimetry has been described where fluorescein was used as the adsorption indicator in conjunction with lead and tin salts. In the present communication attempts have been made to describe the use of fluorescein as an adsorption indicator along with a bismuth salt.

Traces of bismuth subnitrate are added to a solution of nitric acid (not less than $N/5$) and a few drops of fluorescein. The solution is titrated with sodium carbonate or caustic soda. The procedure is the same as in the cases previously described. The equivalent point is marked by a sudden change in colour of the solution from dull green to deep yellow (in case of Na_2CO_3) or reddish yellow (in case of NaOH). The method, however, has a limited application and can be used in titrating nitric acids of moderate dilutions, as bismuth salts are insoluble in very dilute acids. The following table gives an idea of the range within which the method may be used. Eosin may be used instead of fluorescein, in which case the colour changes from dull red to brilliant scarlet.

Approx. strength of acid or alkali.	Vol. of alkaline soln. reqd. for a known vol. of acid (Methyl orange).	Vol. of alkaline soln. for the same vol. acid. (Fluorescein).
2N	15'00 c.c.	15'00 c.c.
N	15'00	15'00
N/2	15'00	15'00
N/5	15'00	15'05

The mechanism of the reaction may be explained as in the previous cases, as the result of adsorption of the dye on the precipitate of bismuth salt, formed by the excess of alkali after the acid is neutralised.

My thanks are due to Prof. A. Maitra for his kind interest in this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received April 4, 1937.

